

MSRBot: Using Bots to Answer Questions from Software Repositories

TABLE I
LIST OF QUESTIONS SUPPORTED BY OUR BOT AND THE RATIONALE FOR THEIR INCLUSION

Question	Rationale	Related Work
Q1. Which commits fixed the bug ticket bug id ?	To refer the commit to a developer who is working on similar bug.	[3]
Q2. Which developer(s) fixes the most bugs related to File Name ?	To know which developer(s) have experience in fixing bugs related to a specific component or file.	[3]
Q3. Which are the most bug introducing files?	To refactor the buggy files in the repository.	[3]
Q4. Who modified File Name ?	To know which developer(s) worked on the file in order to ask them about a piece of code.	[5], [4]
Q5. Which are the bugs introduced by commit Commit Hash ?	To study the type of bugs introduced because of certain commit.	[3]
Q6. What are the number of commits in/on Date ?	To track the progress of the team members at particular time (e.g., in the last day, week, month).	[4]
Q7. What commits were submitted on Date ?	To know exactly what commits were done, to flag for review, testing, integration, etc.	[4]
Q8. What is/are the latest commit(s) to File Name ?	Developers may want to know what are the last things that changed in a file/class to be up o date before they make modifications.	[5], [4], [2]
Q9. What are the commits related to File Name ?	To track changes which are happening on the file which the developer is currently working on it. Or to know the changes happening to a file that was abandoned by a developer.	[1]
Q10. What is/are the most common bug(s)?	The team wants the most important/common bug (registered as watchers) so it can be addressed.	[3]
Q11. What are the buggy/fixing commits that happened Date ?	To know the buggy or fixing commits happened at a particular time e.g. before release date.	[3]
Q12. How many bugs have the status/priority?	Quickly view the number of bug reports with a specific status (e.g., open) or priority (e.g., blocker) plan a fix for it.	[3]
Q13. Who is the author of File Name ?	Developers who have questions about a specific file or class may want to speak to the person who created it.	[6], [5]
Q14. Which developer(s) have the most unfixed bugs?	To determine the overloaded developers and possibly re-assign bugs to others on the team.	[3]
Q15. What is the percentage of bug fixing commits that introduced bugs Date ?	To study the characteristics of the fixing commits which happened at a certain time and induced bugs.	[3]

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Begel, Y. P. Khoo, and T. Zimmermann. Codebook: discovering and exploiting relationships in software repositories. In *2010 ACM/IEEE 32nd International Conference on Software Engineering*, volume 1, pages 125–134, May 2010.
- [2] A. Begel and T. Zimmermann. Appendix to analyze this! 145 questions for data scientists in software engineering - microsoft research. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/publication/appendix-to-analyze-this-145-questions-for-data-scientists-in-software-engineering>. (Accessed on 12/20/2018).
- [3] A. Begel and T. Zimmermann. Analyze this! 145 questions for data scientists in software engineering. In *Proceedings of the 36th International Conference on Software Engineering*, ICSE 2014, pages 12–23, New York, NY, USA, 2014. ACM.
- [4] T. Fritz and G. C. Murphy. Using information fragments to answer the questions developers ask. In *Proceedings of the 32Nd ACM/IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering - Volume 1*, ICSE '10, pages 175–184, New York, NY, USA, 2010. ACM.
- [5] V. S. Sharma, R. Mehra, and V. Kaulgud. What do developers want?: An advisor approach for developer priorities. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Workshop on Cooperative and Human Aspects of Software Engineering*, CHASE '17, pages 78–81, Piscataway, NJ, USA, 2017. IEEE Press.
- [6] J. Sillito, G. C. Murphy, and K. D. Volder. Asking and answering questions during a programming change task. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 34(4):434–451, July 2008.